

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, Alison K. Post, and R. Chelsea Nagy

Landsat 9 Sees Buccaneer Archipelago
by Monika Luabeya
Image credit: NASA/Michala Garrison; USGS

Quick Updates

- Jennifer Balch received the prestigious honor of being named an [AGU Fellow](#).
- The Fire Lab was featured in several news outlets including [NPR](#), [CPR](#), and the [ASCEND Engine](#).
- Earth Lab Director, Virginia Iglesias, was recently featured in two magazine articles: [EOS](#) & [EM](#).
- Jennifer Balch, in collaboration with several Earth Lab members, was awarded an NSF grant to create a "Fast Fire Network" to address increased fire speed under climate change.
- Chelsea Nagy and Alison Post, in collaboration with USDA colleagues, were awarded a Joint Fire Science Program grant to study the flammability of invasive versus native grassland species.
- The MS-CC, ESIL, and Black Codes collaborated for a Student Hackathon. [Read more in a blog](#) written by Education Director, Nathan Quarderer.
- Earth Lab hosted nine undergraduate and graduate students as summer researchers. They worked on a variety of projects, from alpine greening to forest recovery after wildfire.

Earth Lab Turns 10!

Earth Lab is celebrating our 10th birthday! Over the past decade, Earth Lab's contributions have reached far beyond the university. Its research has informed the 2023 Economic Report of the President, shaped proposed EPA air quality standards, and supported real-time risk-reduction strategies for industry partners and emergency managers. Earth Lab scholars actively engage in public discourse, advising policymakers through roundtables with the U.S. Congress, FEMA, and the Department of Homeland Security, and also serve as trusted voices in local and national media. To date, Earth Lab has trained more than 80 undergraduate and graduate students and 18 postdoctoral researchers, published 193 scientific papers, and brought in over \$36 million in external funding—investments that helped launch two major campus centers: the North Central Climate Adaptation Science Center (NC CASC) and the Environmental Data Science Innovation and Impact Lab (ESIL).

Join Us to Celebrate 10 Years!

Join us to celebrate a decade of environmental data science and education! There will be remarks from Earth Lab members, as well as several community-building events. Please register by **Oct 20**. Hope to see you there!

Nov. 4th, 2025

10 AM - 1 PM

SEEC, C120

[RSVP & Learn more](#)

Ecological Society of America's Annual Meeting

In August, five Earth Lab team members presented their work at the Ecological Society of America's annual meeting in Baltimore, MD. They enjoyed presenting research and educational tools, making new connections, and celebrating ecology education and research!

"It was special to gather with ecologists who are all still working on amazing research despite the current challenges. Also, I had fun sharing my MD heritage through a crab feast"
- Alison Post, Earth Lab Program Manager

New Team Members

Earth Lab is growing! We're excited to welcome:

Aashish is a graduate from the Department of Computer Science at CU Boulder. He has research experience in explainability of multi-modal models at the Image and Video Computing Group, CU Boulder and has industry experience in software engineering at Walmart Global Tech. At CIRES, he works across Earth Lab and ESIIIL conducting research in integrating different remote sensing datasets for analyzing fire risk propagation and maintaining the cyber-infrastructure of ESIIIL and Earth Lab.

Aashish Mukund

Danielle Losos

Danielle Losos is a graduate student in the Department of Geography, advised by Dr. Jennifer Balch, and a research assistant at Earth Lab. Danielle employs satellite remote sensing to observe rapid disturbance caused by wildland fire, including active fire spread and post-fire impacts to vegetated ecosystems.

NVIDIA Workshop

Earth Lab and the ASCEND Engine (formerly the CO-WY Engine) collaborated with [NVIDIA](#), a world leader in AI computing, to co-host their Earth-2 Workshop: Framework & Libraries to Enable AI-Augmented Solutions. This workshop was led by NVIDIA scientists on the CU Boulder campus. The goal was to explore tools and infrastructure behind Earth-2, NVIDIA's digital twin platform, and discuss how they can support next-generation environmental modeling and decision-making.

Summer Socials

Over the summer, Earth Lab hosted two social events to bring together team members, summer students, and collaborators. We had an ice cream social to welcome our summer students in early summer and a farewell happy hour to send them off. Thank you to Earth Lab team members and students!

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